

Molecular Dynamics Simulations to Explore the Binding Mode between the Amyloid- β protein Precursor (APP) and Adaptor Protein Mint2

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CPPTRAJ Script:

```
# RMSD, RMSF, Rg, SASA
parm nowat.prmtop
trajin nowat.dcd
rms first mass out rmsd.dat :15-204@CA=
run
atomicfluct byres out rmsf.dat :15-204@CA=
run
radgyr :15-204&!(@H=) out rg.dat mass nomax
run
surf :15-204 out surf.dat
run
# DSSP
parm nowat.prmtop
trajin nowat.dcd
autoimage
secstruct :1-204 out dssp.dat
Run
# B-factor
parm nowat.prmtop
trajin nowat.dcd
atomicfluct out back.apf @C,CA,N byres bfactor
run
# K-means clustering
parm nowat.prmtop
trajin nowat.dcd
strip :Na+,Cl-
cluster c1 kmeans clusters 10 randompoint maxit 500 rms :15-204@C,N,O,CA,CB&!@H=
sieve 10 random out cnumvtime.dat summary summary.dat info info.dat cpopvtime
cproptvtime.agr normframe repout rep repfmt pdb singlerepout singlerep.nc singlerepfmt
netcdf avgout avg avgfmt pdb
run
# PCA
parm nowat.prmtop
trajin nowat.dcd
rms first :15-204&!@H=
average crdset proavy
run
```

```
rms ref proavy :15-204&!@H=  
matrix covar name MyMatrix :15-204&!@H=  
createcrd CRD1  
run  
runanalysis diagmatrix MyMatrix vecs 2 name MyEvecs  
crdaction CRD1 projection evecs MyEvecs :15-204&!@H= out project.dat beg 1 end 2  
quit  
# H-Bond  
parm nowat.prmtop  
trajin nowat.dcd  
hbond donormask :1-14@F=,O=,N= acceptormask :15-204@F=,O=,N= out nhb1.dat avgout  
avghb1.dat  
run  
hbond donormask :15-204@F=,O=,N= acceptormask :1-14@F=,O=,N= out nhb2.dat avgout  
avghb2.dat  
run
```


Figure s1. (A) The temporal evolution of the RMSDs from their initial structures of 4 systems. (B) Relative frequencies of the RMSDs for 4 systems. (C) The temporal evolution of the RMSDs from their initial structures of 4 systems in replica 1. (D) Relative frequencies of the RMSDs for 4 systems in replica 1. (E) The temporal evolution of the RMSDs from their initial structures of 4 systems in replica 2. (F) Relative frequencies of the RMSDs for 4 systems in replica 2. (G) The temporal evolution of the RMSDs from their initial structures of 4 systems in replica 3. (H) Relative frequencies of the RMSDs for 4 systems in replica 3. (I) The temporal evolution of the RMSDs from their initial structures of 4 systems in replica 4. (J) Relative frequencies of the RMSDs for 4 systems in replica 4.

Figure s2. (A) The radius of gyration of 4 systems during 400 ns simulation. (B) Relative frequencies of the Rg values for 4 systems. (C) The radius of gyration of 4 systems during 400 ns simulation in replica 1. (D) Relative frequencies of the Rg values for 4 systems in replica 1. (E) The radius of gyration of 4 systems during 400 ns simulation in replica 2. (F) Relative frequencies of the Rg values for 4 systems in replica 2. (G) The radius of gyration of 4 systems during 400 ns simulation in replica 3. (H) Relative frequencies of the Rg values for 4 systems in replica 3. (I) The radius of gyration of 4 systems during 400 ns simulation in replica 4. (J) Relative frequencies of the Rg values for 4 systems in replica 4.

Figure s3. (A) SASA values of four systems over 400 ns MD. (B) Relative frequencies of the SASA for 4 systems. (C) SASA values of four systems over 400 ns MD in replica 1. (D) Relative frequencies of the SASA for 4 systems in replica 1. (E) SASA values of four systems over 400 ns MD in replica 2. (F) Relative frequencies of the SASA for 4 systems in replica 2. (G) SASA values of four systems over 400 ns MD in replica 3. (H) Relative frequencies of the SASA for 4 systems in replica 3. (I) SASA values of four systems over 400 ns MD in replica 4. (J) Relative frequencies of the SASA for 4 systems in replica 4.

Figure s4. RMSFs of Ca atoms in the four systems: **(A)** free Mint2 and mutant Mint2 free. **(B)** Mint2-APP and mutant Mint2-APP. The major changes in RMSF occur on the residues 40–75 for complexes. **(C)** RMSFs of free Mint2 and mutant Mint2 free in replicate 1. **(D)** RMSFs of Mint2-APP and mutant Mint2-APP in replicate 1. **(E)** RMSFs of free Mint2 and mutant Mint2 free in replicate 2. **(F)** RMSFs of Mint2-APP and mutant Mint2-APP in replicate 2. **(G)** RMSFs of free Mint2 and mutant Mint2 free in replicate 3. **(H)** RMSFs of Mint2-APP and mutant Mint2-APP in replicate 3. **(I)** RMSFs of free Mint2 and mutant Mint2 free in replicate 4. **(J)** RMSFs of Mint2-APP and mutant Mint2-APP in replicate 4

Figure s5. DSSP for entire protein **(A)** Free Mint2. **(B)** Mutant free Mint2. **(C)** Mint2-APP. **(D)** Mutant Mint2-APP.

